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**Critical Thinking, Self-esteem and their
Importance in Writing Performance**

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Abstract

Proficiency in writing is considered a crucial component of language acquisition in the English language. Various tactics are suggested for addressing the obstacles encountered by those learning English as a Second Language or English as a Foreign Language. Hence, the objective of this study is to provide a comprehensive literature analysis on prior research about the correlation and influence of two variables, namely critical thinking and self-esteem, on students' English writing proficiency. The purpose is to investigate if these variables substantially affect writing performance. Based on the results, a significant proportion of the papers were carried out in Asian nations. Most research on the subject has shown that teachers and students in English as a Second Language/English as a Foreign Language writing situations have generally shown a good reception towards critical thinking and self-esteem. Numerous researchers have highlighted the need to incorporate critical thinking and self-esteem into English teaching and learning. This pedagogical method has allowed English language practice within English as a Second Language or as a Foreign Language. Ultimately, it is recommended to use this methodology for English composition instruction since it can potentially cultivate students' aptitude in written expression.

Keywords: *Critical Thinking, Self-Esteem, Writing Performance*

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Introduction

Acquiring critical thinking is an important cognitive skill for learners. Educators and psychologists, like Schafersman (1991), have emphasized the need to incorporate critical thinking skills into the curriculum. The purpose of education is to teach learners how to think critically, enabling them to become effective and competent citizens in the real world (Ido & Jones, 1991). Additionally, Atkinson (1997) asserts that while critical thinking has been widely utilized in first language education in the United States, its role and impact in second and foreign language learning and teaching is also highly significant.

Self-esteem is a psychological and social concept that involves an individual's assessment of their abilities and self-worth based on certain values. This evaluation can lead to various emotional states and remains relatively consistent over time, although it can still be influenced by personal circumstances (Rubio, 2007). Self-esteem has been extensively studied by educators, psychologists, and sociologists, particularly in the context of language learning. As a result, the significance of self-esteem in the language classroom is unquestionable.

Writing is a type of communication that follows certain conventions within various speech communities. These conventions encompass spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and the appropriate structure and vocabulary for a given text. Brown (2000) identifies certain characteristics that contribute to the complexity of writing. Specifically, the complexity is often attributed to the use of clauses in written text. Compared to spoken language, written language tends to have longer clauses and a greater degree of subordination.

Developing writing skills is more challenging compared to listening, speaking, and reading. While many learners can generate ideas in their minds, they struggle to express them on paper. It is common for students to encounter difficulties during the language learning process. However, if these problems begin to interrelate, they can lead to complex issues that are not easily resolved. Therefore, studying the connection between students' weaknesses and strengths can assist education professionals in making accurate predictions and creating effective plans for the teaching-learning process.

Students often experience stress due to various factors such as time constraints, unfamiliar topics, and different writing genres. Second language writing, in particular, presents additional challenges. The development of self-esteem and critical thinking skills is crucial for language learning, particularly in writing. However, many students lack critical thinking abilities. Recent observations and findings indicate that critical thinking occupies a pivotal role in education, necessitating educators to modify their instructional approaches to foster the development of students' essential critical thinking traits. Additionally, low self-esteem and limited language proficiency are common problems among students. These issues can negatively impact a student's motivation, focus, and willingness to take risks in their learning. Conversely, positive self-esteem serves as a solid foundation for academic success.

There exists a compelling need for research endeavors that delve into the importance of self-esteem and critical thinking in augmenting the writing proficiency of individuals acquiring the English language. Consequently, the primary objective of this research is to review the influence of self-esteem and critical thinking on writing proficiency.

In today's environment, we constantly generate words to express our ideas, emotions, and viewpoints. As a result, it is crucial to enhance our writing skills to effectively communicate with others. Having strong writing abilities allows us to convey our message in a clear and concise manner. Moreover, improved writing skills enable us to reach a wider

audience. Whether we are tasked with writing a report, letter, application, or thesis, it is essential to utilize our writing talents to communicate precisely and effectively.

Hence, this research aims to discover the importance of critical thinking in correlation with writing proficiency while also reviewing the role of self-esteem in the writing proficiency of EFL students.

According to Elder (2005), critical thinking is an essential component in the successful teaching of any subject. It should be the central focus of any professional development program. Additionally, according to Rosenberg (1965), the inclusion of self-esteem enhancing subjects inside the educational setting fosters a more significant and integrated atmosphere. On a different note, English learners can enhance their learning experience and improve their writing skills through a deeper understanding of the writing process.

Additionally, this paper contributes to the evaluation of the significance and impact of critical thinking and self-esteem on writing ability. Moreover, the research aims to provide valuable insights into the less explored aspects of this important matter. The results of this research can potentially benefit those involved in EFL learning, including learners, instructors, materials authors, and curriculum creators.

Writing is a crucial skill that enables people to communicate and express their thoughts and ideas. It is an essential part of everyday life, so students need to recognize the importance of acquiring the necessary skills to handle the challenges of writing in a foreign language. Teachers strive to enhance students' writing abilities.

According to the literature, most studies have focused on the relationship between self-esteem and oral skills, neglecting the importance of self-esteem in students' writing performance (Branden, 2001). Additionally, a higher level of critical thinking can enhance learners' ability to express themselves effectively in writing. Therefore, it is crucial for teachers to recognize learners' critical thinking abilities and provide support to help them improve. To the utmost of the researcher's knowledge, there needs to be more particular studies that reviewed the relationship and consequence of critical thinking and self-esteem on the writing performance of learners. According to Oxford and Ehrman (1992), teachers must learn to recognize and understand the significant differences among their students in order to offer insightful method. This is particularly important for raising the velocity of acquisition of a second or foreign language. Additionally, self-esteem plays a crucial role in language learning, as it is necessary for successful cognitive and affective activities (Brown, 2000). Exploring the relationship between self-esteem and language learning strategies can help us comprehend how students perceive themselves, which can impact their writing skills and the strategies they employ for learning. Moreover, obtaining a clear awareness of the importance of critical thinking on writing skills can equip instructors and authorities with valuable insights. This knowledge can enable them to implement appropriate methods tailored to individual differences in order to foster critical thinking among students.

Review of the Related Literature

Definition of Writing

Writing is considered a crucial skill in second language acquisition, and scholars have provided different definitions of it. Chakraverty and Gautum (2000) perceive writing as a reflective task that necessitates the writer to dedicate sufficient time to contemplate the specific topic, analyze and categorize any prior knowledge, and then employ appropriate language to organize these ideas into a coherent discourse. Conversely, Andrews (2001) holds a contrasting perspective,

viewing writing as a multifaceted activity that involves the utilization of imagination, senses, mental state, cognitive state, and various other factors. Abisamara (2001) takes a syntactic approach to writing, viewing it as a process that naturally generates ideas and prioritizes meaning and communication over form and grammar. Shokrpour and Fallahzadeh (2007) offer a more recent definition, describing writing as a multifaceted activity that reflects the writer's communicative abilities. Additionally, Myhill (2009) argues that First Language (L1) writing encompasses three domains: cognitive psychology, socio-cultural factors, and linguistics.

The field of writing instruction in higher learning institutions has gained increasing interest over time. Across the chronicles of language instruction, various approaches have been developed to teach writing, leading to significant changes in the field of language learning. In her work, Raimes (1998) classifies the teaching of writing into four distinct periods. The first period, from 1966 to 1976, was characterized by an emphasis on form. According to Raimes, this period was dominated by the behaviorists' view of language teaching, which required students to memorize language structures. During the second period (1976-1986), the main focus of writing was on the writer themselves. They had the freedom to write in their own unique ways in order to engage the reader or audience. This period emphasized the importance of considering the audience when writing. It marked a shift from solely focusing on the form of writing to also considering how students compose their work. Moving on to the third period (1986-1996), the emphasis shifted to the content of writing. It was believed during this time that the purpose of teaching ESL was to equip learners with the skills needed to successfully complete their academic tasks.

In the fourth period, which began in 1996, the focus of the writing shifted towards academic readers. Teachers and peers of learners were specifically targeted as the intended audience. Prominent academics like Richards and Rodgers (2001) and Raimes (1998) explored various approaches to teaching writing during this time, including the product approach, the process approach, and the genre approach. However, the categorization of these methods is not within the scope of the current study.

Importance of Writing in L2

According to Cushing Weigle (2002), writing was once considered a skill of the well-educated, but today it is important for everyone. However, this statement is no longer valid, especially in the context of EFL learning. It is necessary to provide all EFL learners with the ability to express their thoughts, ideas, and responses in writing. This not only helps them improve their writing skills but also gives them access to better education, employment opportunities, and empowerment. Unlike speaking, writing requires knowledge of the individual's native language due to the differences in form and use between written and spoken language. Additionally, as Cushing Weigle (2002) argues, writing is not only useful for everyday tasks but also essential for professional and academic success. This applies to both the learner's first language and EFL.

Writing is an equally important skill in language learning, along with listening, speaking, and reading. L2 practitioners recognize that writing plays a crucial role in professional, community, and social contexts. It enables L2 students to express themselves, complete important tasks, cultivate critical thinking abilities, and improve cognitive functioning (Graham & Perin, 2007).

Critical Thinking

Definition of Critical Thinking

Defining critical thinking is a complex task as it can vary in meaning among individuals, contexts, and cultures (Halvorsen, 2005). However, as stated by Beyer (1985), despite the existence of diverse definitions, they all highlight the importance of the ability and inclination to gather, evaluate, and utilize information effectively. Various scholars have provided their own definitions of this cognitive skill, which are presented below.

In light of Angelo's (1995) research, critical thinking involves deliberately deploying rational and complex cognitive capacities such as analysis, synthesis, problem detection and resolution, inference, and evaluation. Critical thinking, as defined by Scriven and Paul (1996), is the process of systematically and rigorously conceiving, analyzing, applying, synthesizing, and evaluating knowledge gleaned via observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication. This method provides a structure for forming opinions and directing behavior.

According to Beyer (1995), critical thinking involves making reasoned judgments. Similarly, the capacity to evaluate, critique, and argue for ideas, as well as reason inductively and deductively, leading to factual or evaluative findings based on reasonable inferences taken from clear information or belief, is what Freely and Steinberg (2000) imply by critical thinking.

Significance of Teaching Critical Thinking

In recent decades, researchers have observed that traditional teaching approaches have been ineffective in fully developing learners' abilities. As a result, significant efforts have been made to develop innovative methods and techniques to enhance learning. One such method is CT, which can be traced back to Socrates (Condon & KellyRiley, 2004).

Critical thinking (CT) is often regarded as an essential goal in the classroom (Kuhn, cited in Condon & Kelly Riley, 2004). The importance of critical thinking as a cornerstone of education is emphasized by Woodward (as stated in Twyman, Ketterlin-Geller, McCoy, & Tindal, 2003). Student achievement, he believes, should be gauged not only by how much they learn but also by how well they put what they learn to use. This progression from abstract ideas to practical examples requires the cultivation of critical thinking abilities.

According to Davidson (1998), in the age of technology, individuals cannot simply passively receive information. Instead, they require guidance to critically reflect upon the vast amount of information available. Critical thinking (CT) allows students to assess, investigate, and resolve issues using sound reasoning, as further explained by Condon and Kelly-Riley (2004). It also encourages learners to explore various concepts rather than directly instructing them, thus promoting long-term retention of knowledge. This approach necessitates learners to actively participate and engage in the learning process.

Self-Esteem

Rosenberg (1965) provided a definition of self-esteem as an attitude toward a specific object, the self. Therefore, Rosenberg (1965) integrated emotive and cognitive evaluations of one's value when considering the impact of social variables on one's sense of self-worth. He concluded that one must first set specific criteria and ideals to assess oneself, which must incorporate social aspects. Therefore, one's sense of self-worth increases as the distance between themselves and those ideals narrows.

According to Coopersmith (1967), self-esteem is the individual's evaluation and ongoing perception of themselves, reflecting their position of support or opposition and their belief in their own capabilities. Coopersmith (1967) proposed that emotions like fear and despair are linked to self-esteem. He was the first theorist to propose that self-esteem consists of efficacy and worthiness. Branden (2001) also emphasized the significance of self-evaluation, stating that it affects behavior, thinking, values, desires, goals and emotions. Branden believes that a person's self-image greatly influences their reactions.

Therefore, he focused on the connection between humanistic vision and self-esteem and stated that maintaining a robust impression of self-esteem throughout one's lifetime is fundamental. Moreover, self-confidence is the perception of effectiveness, and self-respect is the sense of worthiness, according to Branden (2001).

Method

The research was conducted using a methodology referred to as a literature review, which included the identification, selection, analysis, interpretation, and integration of previously published scholarly articles or data relevant to the subject matter of critical thinking, self-esteem, and students' writing proficiency. Gibbs et al. (2017) argue that using literature reviews to assess educators' capacities is deemed acceptable since it enables the provision of accurate and reliable assessments. This specific research study examined the impact of including a literature review, as well as other aspects of critical thinking and self-esteem, on enhancing students' ability to contribute to the process of writing. Incorporating these components has been shown to improve teachers' knowledge and professionalism during their stint at the institution, potentially yielding advantages for teachers working in higher education.

Discussion

Critical thinking is a valuable approach that guides learners to reach their highest potential, making it a significant factor in the effectiveness of writing. Despite the strong connection between students' writing and critical thinking, many students fail to demonstrate critical thinking in their writing, while most instructors overlook its crucial role. Numerous studies have emphasized the importance of critical thinking, particularly in developing writing skills for second or foreign language learners.

Regarding the importance of critical thinking (CT), a study involving 160 EFL students was carried out by Gorjian, Pazhakh, and Parangand (2012). This research is to check out the result of critical thinking instructions on the descriptive writing of EFL students. Additionally, the study sought to find out if a notable gender disparity exists in methods used throughout the writing process. The findings demonstrated that providing Iranian EFL students with lessons on critical thinking had a significant impact on the improvement of their descriptive writing. In addition, the studies showed that there were significant differences on the efficient implementation of critical thinking instructions with regard to gender in descriptive writing test performance. These differences were found in relation to the effectiveness of the test takers.

In the similar vein, Shangarffam and Mamipour (2011) conducted research to investigate the effect that teaching critical thinking has on the writing ability of Iranian EFL students. In this particular investigation, they made use of the critical thinking skills suggested by Halvorsen (2005), which included Debate, Media Analysis, and Problem-Solving. The findings of their investigation demonstrated a major impact associated with the instruction of critical thinking skills on the intermediate students' writing ability. The findings imply a substantial rise in the participants' writing proficiency. The implementation of critical thinking education, which involves active student engagement and discourse, proved to be more

effective in fostering students' enthusiasm for writing when compared to the use of cooperative learning strategies. The students' enjoyment of critical thinking activities engaged them in the process of writing and the development of arguments. Thus, students' interest can be considered as a justification for the difference found in this study between cooperative learning and critical thinking.

In an additional research endeavor, Hashemi, Behrooznia, and Mahjoobi (2014) examined Iranian university students' cognitive abilities concerning argumentative writing skills and critical thinking, specifically within the context of EFL acquisition. The study's results offered empirical evidence to substantiate a positive association between critical thinking proficiency and argumentative writing. This suggests that the two variables exhibited a substantial and beneficial relationship. The study's findings also indicated that inference, assumptions, and argumentation were the primary factors that significantly influenced critical thinking. Furthermore, it was shown that there was no substantial impact of gender on the argumentative writing accomplishment of Iranian EFL learners.

Fahim and Mirzaii (2014) conducted a study to examine the impact of a critical thinking strategy on the argumentative writing skills of EFL students. The researchers selected 48 Iranian EFL students using cluster sampling and randomly assigned them to either the experimental group or the control group. The experimental group received writing instruction along with tasks that involved critical thinking, while the control group only received writing instruction. Both groups were instructed to write. The results showed that the combination of critical thinking and writing instruction resulted in higher scores, although both groups demonstrated significant improvements in their ability to write argumentatively.

Srinawati and Alwi (2020) conducted research to investigate the impact of incorporating critical thinking into argumentative writing on learners' utilization of critical thinking skills. The research used a quasi-experimental approach, including a control group and an intervention group. The quantitative analysis of the data revealed that the experimental group significantly outperformed the control group. While the students' proficiency in utilizing credible evidence, addressing counterarguments, supporting conclusions, and constructing a coherent argument in their writings did not achieve a high enough level of proficiency on the posttest, their average level of achievement was promising considering the limited duration of the training they received. Extending the integration of critical thinking over a longer period may yield more encouraging results. Argumentative writing is a crucial aspect of academic writing for second-language learners. Data analysis also indicated that the rhetorical aspects of English argumentative writing were perceived as challenging by most participants. Furthermore, participants primarily employed cognitive, social, and search strategies, with metacognitive strategies being utilized infrequently.

Using a quantitative method, Yundayani (2021) analyzed the relationship between students' critical thinking skills and their ability to compose influential argumentative papers. Sixty-two pupils from a Jakarta-based private vocational school participated in the research. Twenty-five pupils were chosen at random as the sample. Information was gathered using Watson-Glaser theory-based critical thinking and argumentative text composition tests. Researcher used the Lilliefors test, linearity, and analysis of variance. Students who scored higher on the necessary thinking exam also performed better in producing argumentative writing, and the opposite was also true. The research also showed a correlation between students' critical thinking and their ability to write convincing arguments.

The significance of affect, as well as actual levels of self-esteem, in a classroom setting for a language is both entirely obvious and unchallengeable. Furthermore, it is believed that doing research about self-esteem and language acquisition, especially writing ability, would

assist understand how students perceive themselves, and this may impact the sort of learning techniques they utilize as well as how they use those approaches.

According to the subject matter, this article discusses the results of various research that found a positive association between high self-esteem and excellent writing skills. Pajares and Johnson (1993) looked at the connections between self-esteem and the quality of one's writing. According to the findings, there is a correlation between self-esteem and writing performance on the one hand, and writing apprehension and writing self-efficacy on the other. The fact that there is a positive correlation between self-esteem and writing performance lends support to the idea that students' levels of confidence in their writing ability are directly related to the quality of their written work.

Fahim and Rad (2012) conducted a study to investigate the connection between self-esteem levels and paragraph writing ability among Iranian EFL students. The research involved senior students of English as a foreign language, both male and female, who were enrolled at Tonekabon and Lahijan Azad Universities. The findings revealed a significant correlation between self-esteem levels and paragraph writing scores. Consequently, it can be inferred that self-esteem is linked to writing performance.

In his study on the connection between self-esteem and writing achievement, Fifty Union County College students were chosen at random by Gordnick (1996). The study aimed to determine whether and how students' sense of self-esteem affects how well they write. To measure self-esteem, Gordnick utilized Coopersmith's self-esteem exam, while writing skills were evaluated based on the students' grades on the writing assignment. Students' levels of self-esteem were shown to be unrelated to the quality of their written work.

Similarly, Hassan (2001) conducted a study exploring the relationship between the quantity and quality of students' writing, their writing apprehension, and their self-esteem in regards to writing in English as a foreign language. The findings revealed a negative correlation between the level of writing anxiety experienced by EFL students and their self-esteem. Students with lower anxiety levels displayed higher self-esteem, while those with higher anxiety levels exhibited lower self-esteem. Additionally, students with lower anxiety levels demonstrated stronger writing skills compared to those with higher anxiety levels, and vice versa.

Furthermore, Al-Hattab (2006) conducted a study investigating the relationship between students' self-esteem levels and their writing achievements during their time in secondary school in Saudi Arabia. A three-part questionnaire (A, B, and C) was used to evaluate respondents' self-esteem. Objectively measuring global, situational, and task-specific self-esteem was the goal of Section A, Section B, and Section C, respectively. The study's findings indicated that there is no noteworthy correlation between possessing a positive level of self-esteem and being proficient in writing. Based on these statistical results, the author arrived at the aforementioned conclusion.

Conclusion

Based on some studies, learners who have a stronger capacity for critical thinking may be better equipped to write in a complex manner and appropriately convey their goals throughout their writing (Gorjian et al., 2012; Shangarffam & Mamipour, 2011; Hashemi et al., 2014; Fahim & Mirzaii, 2014; Srinawati and Alwi, 2021; Yundayani, 2021). Additionally, throughout the reviewed research, certain scholars have posited that a direct correlation exists between an individual's level of self-esteem and their ability in the domain of writing. (Pajares & Johnson, 1993; Fahim & Rad, 2012). While several scholars have posited the existence of a linear relationship between an individual's self-esteem and their success in writing tasks. (Gordnick, 1996; Hassan, 2001; Al-Hattab, 2006).

Therefore, to be able to have an effective teaching and learning in EFL writing which is a crucial skill in learners' future and academic success, practicing appropriate methods play a significant role. The reviews of this study have revealed that practicing critical thinking skills is a more effective approach in improving EFL learners' writing as compared with cooperative learning. Therefore, it makes sense to exert efforts to include critical thinking abilities in teaching writing.

Additionally, self-esteem has major consequences on students' psychological and personality development within a teaching environment. It can be seen as the ratio between one's abilities or achievements and one's expectations, essentially representing the value one places on success within different areas of competence. Numerous research studies have been undertaken on the contribution of self-esteem to writing abilities in second and foreign language learners, acknowledging its importance. Some of these studies have found that students' writing success is influenced by their level of self-esteem, with low self-esteem students often experiencing writing apprehension. Nevertheless, it is imperative to acknowledge that other research has shown inconclusive evidence about the association between self-esteem and writing proficiency. In light of this, giving learners many opportunities to cultivate their self-esteem as a fundamental psychological element in language acquisition is crucial. The impact of learners' self-esteem on their selection of language learning techniques is substantial.

Therefore, it would be beneficial for teachers to pay closer attention to their students' self-esteem levels and actively work towards enhancing them. It is crucial for teachers to view self-esteem as an overall perception individuals have about themselves over time, rather than just a fleeting feeling experienced during the learning process.

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